

Development of a Grounding System Circuit Model for Transient Analysis Based on Frequency Spectrum of Lightning Current

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Abstract—Ground Potential Rise (GPR) generated by lightning strikes can result in hazardous voltages near hit structure. In this context, several models have been developed in the literature to accurately represent the grounding systems of Lightning Protection Systems (LPS), taking into account more realistic soil characteristics. Utilizing an appropriate model that generates approximate results for diverse LPS geometries, a direct time-domain assessment of GPR can provide an efficient and fast estimation. This is particularly valuable in the development of practical resources for LPS projects, encompassing the analysis of physical installation aspects and the evaluation of risks linked to concealed grid ruptures or disconnections, and potential enhancements through alterations in electrode geometries and positioning. The influence of frequency-dependent soil parameters (FDSP) is crucial and cannot be overlooked when attempting to realistically express GPR, especially for higher soil resistivity. This article introduces a method known as the Filtered Frequency Spectrum Method (FFSM) to efficiently evaluate GPR while considering FDSP. The simulations utilize a simplified grounding system circuit model incorporated into ATP-EMTP software. The frequency spectrum of the lightning current is obtained through a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT); the spectrum is then segmented into bands using filters to select a representative frequency where the FDSP are evaluated. For each band, a circuit model is constructed using Transmission Line Modeling. The resulting GPR is calculated as the sum of the filtered results. Results demonstrated that the GPR calculated using the FFSM presents a good agreement compared with those assessed with traditional recursive methods. The performance of the FFSM is better for soils of low and moderate resistivity and does not require the traditional frequency-to-time conversion tools.

Index Terms—electromagnetic transients, lightning, wind turbines, grounding system

I. INTRODUCTION

Lightning protection systems (LPS) are essential for safeguarding infrastructure, equipment, and personnel from the destructive effects of lightning strikes and for minimizing power system disruptions. The primary function of an LPS is to safely dissipate lightning strike energy into the ground. A critical parameter in evaluating the effectiveness of an LPS is the ground potential rise (GPR), which measures the electric potential resulting from large current flows into the ground in relation to a remote point.

One way to calculate the GPR of an LPS is by constructing an in-depth model of the LPS grid using full-wave electromagnetic software such as Altair's FEKOTM or CDEGSTM. This involves deriving the harmonic impedance and considering frequency-dependent soil parameters (FDSP). After determining the impedance (frequency spectrum - FS) of the electrode model and modelling the lightning current, the next step is to calculate the time-domain GPR using methods such as Vector Fitting (VF), which represents the electrode FS by a circuit model. However, integrating all LPS components into a single system is a complex process and, in many situations, an approximate but fast time-domain solution with controlled error margins is preferred [1]. Such solutions are valuable for preliminary GPR analysis within a grid, enabling exploration of grid rupture scenarios and facilitating rapid adjustments, additions, suppression, or relocation of electrode components.

Numerical electromagnetic analyses have been widely used to model parts of LPS by solving Maxwell's equations in their integral forms through various numerical methods. Notable achievements in this area include the numerical integration of Sommerfeld integrals using the Method of Moments (MOM) and the application of the Finite Element Method (FEM) for solving Maxwell's equations [2]. In contrast, due to its straightforward parameter calculations based on established formulae, the Transmission Line Modelling (TLM) method is extensively utilized for evaluating time-domain voltages along electrodes.

Several studies have extended this method to enhance its accuracy (the results deviate at high frequencies [3]), although at the cost of additional computational efforts. These extensions primarily focus on effectively representing mutual coupling between different parts of the grid [4].

This paper proposes a direct time-domain GPR calculation method, bypassing the need for frequency spectrum (FS) conversion tools. This is achieved by considering a more realistic ground using its frequency-dependent soil parameters (FDSP). The method uses the lightning stroke (LS) current spectrum divided into frequency bands, where a representative frequency is selected based on the energy density within each band. This is denoted as the Filtered Frequency Spectrum Method (FFSM). Three different approaches to select this

representative frequency in each band are developed. Then, the frequency-dependent parameters, electrical resistivity and permittivity, are calculated at each specific frequency. Finally, a simplified grounding system circuit model is created for each band, and the resulting voltage is the sum of the individual outputs. The GPR developed for lightning currents representative of the first and subsequent injected into a horizontal electrode buried in soils of 100, 1,000 and 10,000 $\Omega \cdot m$ are evaluated using the FFSM. Results demonstrated that the GPR calculated using the FFSM presents a good agreement compared with those assessed with traditional recursive methods. The performance of the FFSM is better for soils of low and moderated resistivity. This FFSM is based on a simplified grounding system circuit model where only few frequency bands are used instead of the traditional frequency-conversion tools where the full frequency spectrum must be used for the assessment of transient GPR.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. The parameters of a buried electrode

In this section, the three fundamental parameters of a wire conductor shall be analyzed (Resistance \mathfrak{R} to the soil, Capacitance C , and the self-inductance L); the respective formulae shall be demonstrated and discussed as per the conditions they are applied.

Soil is a crucial element in planning the Lightning Protection System (LPS); its parameters, resistivity and permittivity, vary with distinct factors such as composition, temperature, moisture content, and seasonal and weather changes. The proper LPS design, including electrode length, use of vertical rods, and mesh grid dimensions, depends on soil parameters. The ground resistance \mathfrak{R} measures the ratio between the conductor voltage and the current flowing into the soil, assuming a low-frequency disturbance or at the steady state condition. The \mathfrak{R} is directly related to soil resistivity and ground system geometry, where the resulting Ground Potential Rise (GPR) develops during lightning transients and requires special attention from designers.

It is considered a cylindrical wire of radius a immersed in the soil of resistivity ρ (Fig.1). The wire is positioned along the y-axis, and a current $I(u)$ flows into the soil from a specific position $x = u$ on the wire. A point $P(x, y)$ is considered in the soil at the distance given by $s = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$ from $x = u$. An equal distribution of current $I(u)$ flowing into the soil at a distance s from an element du can be represented by that current $I(u)$ through a surface area of a sphere (area = $4\pi s^2$). Based on this assumption and that the current density $J(s) = E(s)/\rho$ at a distance s from $x = u$, the electrical field $E(s)$ at s can be written as:

$$E(s) = \frac{\rho}{4\pi s^2} I(u) \quad (1)$$

The electric potential $V(x, y)$ depends on its physical distribution along the wire buried in the soil and its flowing current.

The potential is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} V(x, y) &= \int_s^\infty E(s) ds = \int_s^\infty \frac{I(u)\rho}{4\pi s^2} ds = \frac{I(u)\rho}{4\pi} \int_s^\infty \frac{1}{s^2} ds = \\ &= \frac{I(u)\rho}{4\pi s} = \frac{I(u)\rho}{4\pi \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

With the previous preamble to generalized a wire conductor located in the soil, the fundamental equations from [5] are quickly introduced; in this work, it is considered a conductor of length l represented along x-axis ($-l/2 \leq x \leq l/2$); the current $I(0)$ is injected in conductor position $x = 0$; the current $dI(u)$ flows to the soil from conductor element du and produces the potential $dV(x, y)$ at a point x, y (eq. 3a). Equation 3a is integrated over $-l/2 \leq x \leq l/2$ resulting in 3b. From this equation, some discussions are done to understand how the soil resistance \mathfrak{R} is obtained and point out the approximation and constraints the formulae consider.

$$dV(x, y) = \frac{dI(u)}{du} \frac{\rho}{4\pi} [(x - u)^2 + y^2]^{-1/2} du \quad (3a)$$

$$V(x, y) = \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} \frac{\rho}{4\pi} [(x - u)^2 + y^2]^{-1/2} \frac{d(I(u))}{du} du \quad (3b)$$

As indicated in [5], the current leaving the conductor ($c1$) is considered to be at the x-axis, and for this reason, it is taken as a long conductor as per ratio l/a ; another condition ($c2$) is the conductor resistance which is considered negligible, resulting in null potential differences along the conductor. Based on conditions $c1$ and $c2$, at the conductor surface and along it, the potential does not vary and thus $dV(x, a)/dx = 0$, as seen in 4a.

$$0 = \frac{d}{dx} \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} \frac{\rho}{4\pi} [(x - u)^2 + a^2]^{-1/2} \frac{d(I(u))}{du} du \quad (4a)$$

$$V(x, y) = \frac{2I(0)\rho}{4\pi l} \ln(\alpha(x, y)) \quad (4b)$$

$$\alpha(x, y) = \frac{\sqrt{(x + l/2)^2 + y^2} + (x + l/2)}{\sqrt{(x - l/2)^2 + y^2} + (x - l/2)} \quad (4c)$$

The [5] mentions a solution to equation 4a and highlights there is a viable solution in case $dI(u)/du$ is made equal to the average leaking current I_0/l . Thus equation 3b turns into 4b. Integrating 4b the resistance \mathfrak{R} of a conductor in a medium of infinite extent is obtained 6a, usually present in its approximate form 6b.

The relative error E_R for the wire resistance to the soil when \mathfrak{R}_A is used instead of \mathfrak{R} is indicated in Fig. 2. The wire radius ranges from 1 to 7 mm in this example, and five different wire lengths were considered: 3, 12, 25, 50, and 100 m. The respective typical wire cross-sectional areas (16, 35, 50, 95, and 150 mm²) usually utilized for grounded electrodes are indicated in the figure. The relative error 5 increases as the radius increases, while it decreases for longer wire lengths. Notice that the error is kept below 0.05% in all cases.

$$E_R(\%) = \frac{\mathfrak{R} - \mathfrak{R}_A}{\mathfrak{R}} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1: Generic wire buried in a lossy soil.

Fig. 2: Relative Error for different wire radius and length.

$$\Re = \frac{\rho}{l} \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{a} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{a}{l} \right)^2} \right) + \frac{a}{l} - 1 + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{a}{l} \right)^2} \right) \right) \quad (6a)$$

$$\Re_A = \frac{\rho}{2\pi l} \left[\ln \left(\frac{2l}{a} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (6b)$$

The capacitance C is expressed as the fundamental equation $C = Q/V$ and the the Resistance to soil as the equation $\Re = V/I$. As per definition, the capacitance occurs between two charged conductors elements. In the case of a charged conductor immersed in the soil, it represents the ratio of charge between the conductor and the soil, and the generated potential difference . The equations 7c include the ratio for the capacitance and Resistance to soil, considering the Ohm's law ($\oint \sigma E \cdot dS$) and the Gauss' law ($Q = \oint \epsilon E \cdot dS$), as seen in 7 which express the parameters in terms of soil conductance σ and electrical permittivity ϵ ;

$$C = \frac{Q}{V} = \frac{\oint \epsilon E \cdot dS}{\int E \cdot dl}, \quad (7a)$$

$$\Re = \frac{V}{I} = \frac{\int E \cdot dl}{\oint \sigma E \cdot dS}, \quad (7b)$$

$$C = \frac{1}{\epsilon \rho \Re} \quad (7c)$$

As a result, the capacitance C is directly expressed in terms of \Re and those soil electrical parameters, and the soil resistivity expression $\rho = 1/\sigma$;

The self-inductance L may be calculated by the Bio-Savart law 8. Considering a straight wire of length l , distributed along axe y ($0 \leq y \leq l$), and a point P distant b from the wire, P is initially located at $(b, 0)$, on the perpendicular axe x that intercepts axe y on P' , and this point is initially located at $(0, 0)$; a current I flows in the wire and a current element dI on position $(0, y)$, distant r from P , causes an elementary magnetic field $d\vec{H}$ on position $(b, 0)$.

$$d\vec{B} = \mu_0 d\vec{H} = \frac{\mu_0 I d\vec{l} \times \hat{r}}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{\mu_0 I d\vec{l} \times R}{4\pi r^3} \quad (8)$$

As per definition the magnetic field is expressed as $d\vec{H} = Id\vec{y} \sin \theta \hat{v}_\phi / (b^2 + y^2)$. Considering that $|R| = \sqrt{b^2 + y^2}$, $b = \sin \phi \sqrt{b^2 + y^2}$ and the unitary vectors $\hat{v}_\phi = \hat{v}_y \times \hat{v}_r$, the elementary magnetic field is expressed as:

$$d\vec{H} = I b d\vec{y} \times \hat{v}_r / (\sqrt{b^2 + y^2})^{3/2} = I b \hat{v}_\phi / (\sqrt{b^2 + y^2})^{3/2} \quad (9)$$

This function is subjected to integrals, as per (10), to find the magnetic flux B . The first integral is done on y from $(0, 0)$ to $(0, l)$, representing the magnetic field on the point P from all components $I dy$; the second integral is done on y from $(b, 0)$ to (b, l) , representing all the magnetic field components along axe (b, y) . The third integral is done on x from a to ∞ , representing the total magnetic flux to which the wire is subjected from its surface (wire radius= a). Notice that the integral is done two times as the magnetic field on a point (b, y) depends not only on the elementary currents from $(0, y)$ to $(0, l)$ but also from $(0, 0)$ to $(0, l)$. The inductance definition is the ratio between the total magnetic flux Ψ and the current 10. The flux Ψ is the integral of the magnetic flux density B over the considered area, expressed as follows:

$$\Psi = \int B \cdot dS, \quad (10a)$$

$$\Psi = \frac{\mu_0 I}{4\pi} \int_0^\infty 2 \int_0^l \int_0^l \frac{b}{(b^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} dy dx, \quad (10b)$$

$$\Psi = \frac{\mu_0 I}{4\pi} \int_0^\infty 2 \int_0^l \frac{y}{b \sqrt{b^2 + y^2}} dy dx, \quad (10c)$$

$$\Psi = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2\pi} \int_a^\infty \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + l^2}}{x} - 1 \right) dx, \quad (10d)$$

$$\Psi = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2\pi} l \left[\ln \left(\frac{l + \sqrt{l^2 + a^2}}{a} \right) - \sqrt{l^2 + a^2} + a \right], \quad (10e)$$

$$L = \frac{\Psi}{I} \approx l \frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{2l}{a} - 1 \right). \quad (10f)$$

B. Transmission Line Modeling

The Transmission Line Model (TLM) uses circuitual modeling (cascaded π -circuit) to represent the wave propagation along a conductor. The wire segment must be much smaller than one-tenth of the current spectrum minimum wavelength [6]. As per formula deductions and analysis in Section II-A, and in case the burial depth d may be neglected with respect of

Fig. 3: Transmission line model for: (a) a buried horizontal electrode; (b) Longitudinal and transversal currents; (c) elemental circuit for a differential segment of length dx .

the electrode length l , ($l \gg d$), the per-unit-length parameters conductor resistance R , the self inductance L , the capacitance C , and conductance $G = 1/\Re$ are expressed in (11).

$$R = \frac{\rho_c}{\pi a^2}, L = \frac{\mu}{2\pi} \kappa, C = \frac{2\pi\epsilon}{\kappa}, G = \frac{2\pi}{\rho \kappa}, \quad (11a)$$

$$\kappa = \ln \left(\frac{2l}{\sqrt{d2a}} - 1 \right), \quad (11b)$$

$$\kappa' = \frac{1}{2} \left[\ln \left(\frac{2l}{a} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{l}{d} \right) - 2 + \frac{2d}{l} - \frac{d^2}{l^2} + \frac{d^4}{2l^4} + \dots \right] \quad (11c)$$

where ρ_c is the conductor resistivity, and a is the radius of the conductor section. The constant κ in (11-(b)) may be replaced by κ' as per (11-(c)) κ' is also valid for ($l \gg d$) [7].

The harmonic impedance $Z(j\omega)$ are defined in (12).

$$Z(j\omega) = Z_C \coth(\gamma l), \quad (12)$$

where Z_C is the characteristic impedance and γ is the propagation constant, expressed by:

$$Z_C(j\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{Z_L}{Z_T}} \quad (13a)$$

$$\gamma(j\omega) = \sqrt{Z_L Z_T} \quad (13b)$$

where $Z_L(j\omega) = R + j\omega L$ is the longitudinal impedance and $Z_T(j\omega) = G + j\omega C$ is the transversal admittance.

The soil parameters (ρ, ϵ) are dependent with the frequency due to the several polarization in the soil particles. This characteristic was first proved based on empirical measurements, as detailed in [8]. Complying with FDSP in simulations brings the system into a much more realistic condition. The GPR peak value is lower than that obtained using FC (constant soil

Fig. 4: GPR obtained using distinct blocks containing the Transfer Functions (TF) representing the filtering method.

parameters). The FDSP expressions used in this work are given by [8], [9].

$$\sigma(f) = \sigma_0 + \sigma_0 \times h(\sigma_0) \left(\frac{f}{1MHz} \right)^f \quad (14a)$$

$$\epsilon_r(f) = \frac{\epsilon'_\infty}{\epsilon_0} + \frac{\tan(\pi\gamma/2) 10^{-3}}{2\pi\epsilon_0 (1MHz)^\gamma} \sigma_0 \times h(\sigma_0) f^{\gamma-1} \quad (14b)$$

where f is the cyclic frequency (Hz), σ_0 is low-frequency (or DC) conductivity (mS/m), $h(\sigma_0)$ represents the DC conductivity between 100 Hz and 1 MHz, γ is a coefficient associated to the ground. The ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity ($\epsilon_0 = 8.854 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m), the $\epsilon'_\infty/\epsilon_0$ is the ratio of relative permittivity at high frequencies. The values adopted in this work are: $\epsilon'_\infty/\epsilon_0 = 12$, $h(\sigma_0) = 1.26\sigma_0^{-0.73}$ and $\gamma = 0.54$, based on [10].

C. Fundamentals for the FFSM

In Fig.4, in case no filters are applied to the input signal, $V(s) = Z(s)I(s)$ is an elementary transfer function (TF) of a circuit model, and $Z(s)$ represents its frequency domain impedance which is subjected to the time-domain input current $i(t)$; $v(t)$ is the output voltage. An equivalent TF is obtained in case only filters $F_{1L}(s)$ and $F_{1H}(s)$ are applied (low and high pass ideal filters using the same cutoff frequency).

$$\mathcal{L}\{v_1(t) + v_2(t)\} = \mathcal{L}\{v_1(t)\} + \mathcal{L}\{v_2(t)\} \quad (15a)$$

$$v(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{V(s)\} = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{\mathcal{L}\{v_1(t)\} + \mathcal{L}\{v_2(t)\}\} \quad (15b)$$

For TF using only filters $F_{1L}(s)$ $F_{1H}(s)$, and using the Laplace Transform properties (15a) and (15b), the output signal (t) results in a sum of filtered signals $v_1(t)$, $v_2(t)$.

In (16a) and (16b) the set of filters produces no impact on the output signal $V(s)$. The TF in (16b) may be rewritten as (17) using F_{1L} and F_{1H} as first order filters, for instance.

$$V(s) = I(s) F_{1L}(s) Z(s) + I(s) F_{1H}(s) Z(s) \quad (16a)$$

$$V(s) = I(s)G(s) = I(s) \{Z(s) [F_{1L}(s) + F_{1H}(s)]\} \quad (16b)$$

$$Z(s) [1 + (1/\omega_C)s]^{-1} + ((1/\omega_C)s) (1 + (1/\omega_C)s)^{-1}] \quad (17)$$

Generalizing filters representation, $F_{(k-1)L}$ and F_{kH} ($1 \leq k \leq n$; k, n positive integers), an n -band Laplace Transfer Function $G(s)$ (Fig. 4) is expressed in (18) (F_{0H} is an ideal high pass filter of the entire spectrum; F_{nH} is a high pass filter from the maximum frequency band on-wards).

$$V(s) = I(s) \left\{ Z(s) \left[\sum_{i=1}^n F_{(i-1)H}(s) F_{iL}(s) \right] \right\} \quad (18)$$

The Eq. (18) may be simplified as (19) as $H_k(j\omega) = 1$, for $\omega_k \leq \omega \leq \omega_k + \Delta\omega_S/n$, and $H_k(j\omega) = 0$ otherwise. $H_k(j\omega)$ is a band pass filter equivalent to $F_{(k-1)H}(j\omega)F_{kL}(j\omega)$. $\Delta\omega_S$ is the frequency spectrum (FS) bandwidth divided in n equal bands. ω_k is the lower frequency of band k with bandwidth $\Delta\omega_S/n$. As the impedance $Z(j\omega)$ depends on the frequency variant soil parameters, it can be represented as $Z(j\omega, \rho(\omega), \epsilon(\omega))$. $Z(s)$ (Fig.4) may refer to an electrical circuit. The FDSP implies that there shall also be frequency dependency on the circuit's electrical parameters.

$$V(j\omega) = I(j\omega) \left\{ Z(j\omega) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n H_k(j\omega) \right] \right\} \quad (19)$$

The capacitance and inductance of a buried electrode are calculated based on ρ and ϵ , selecting the representative frequency restricted to each band. Considering the ideal function $Z(j\omega, \rho(\omega), \epsilon(\omega))$ and the conservative function $Z(j\omega, \rho, \epsilon)$, with fixed soil parameters, there is an in-between function $Z_k(j\omega, \rho(\omega_{ki}), \epsilon(\omega_{ki}))$ which is, for band k frequencies, an approximation for the former and improvement for the latter. ρ_k and ϵ_k , are constant and calculated out of band k frequency spectrum. Thus, (20) represents an approximation for (19).

$$V(j\omega) = I(j\omega) \left[\sum_{k=1}^n Z_k(j\omega, \rho_k, \epsilon_k) H_k(j\omega) \right] \quad (20)$$

As $\sigma(\omega)$ ($1/\rho(\omega)$) and $\epsilon(\omega)$ are increasing and decreasing functions, the inequalities in (21) are true. As the number of bands increases, $Z_k(j\omega, \rho_k, \epsilon_k)$ approximates $Z(j\omega, \rho(\omega), \epsilon(\omega))$ in band k . If $n \rightarrow +\infty$, the second inequality of (21) turns into an equality.

$$\int_0^{\omega_n} Z_0 d\omega \geq \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{\omega_k}^{\omega_k + \frac{\Delta\omega_S}{n}} Z_k d\omega \geq \int_0^{\omega_n} Z d\omega \quad (21)$$

The second concept held in this article refers to the lightning stroke (LS) Energy (all the LS parameters are defined in [11]). The input signal impinged upon the electrode is the LS current $f(t)$. Its Fourier Transform (FT) is $F(\omega)$. As $\mathcal{F}\{f(t)\} = F(\omega)$, its total energy E_T is expressed as per (22).

$$E_T = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f^2(t) dt = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |F(\omega)|^2 d\omega \quad (22)$$

The FS $F(\omega)$ in (22) may be submitted to contiguous band-pass filters $H_k(\omega)$ causing no impact on E_T (22). Thus its integrand $|F(\omega)|^2$ may be written as $|F(\omega)|^2 (|\sum_{k=1}^n H_k(\omega)|)^2$. Since $H_j(\omega)H_k(\omega) = 0$ in case $j \neq k$, and $|H_k(\omega)|^2 = 1$, the energy density spectrum is expressed in (23).

$$E_T = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |F(\omega)|^2 |H_k(\omega)|^2 \right) d\omega \quad (23)$$

If the FS $F(\omega)$ is divided into n parts of bandwidth $\Delta\omega$, the total spectrum energy may be obtained by the sum of all filtered energy bands $F_k(\omega)$ as expressed in (24).

$$E_T = \sum_{k=1}^n E_k = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{\omega_k}^{\omega_k + \Delta\omega} |F_k(\omega)|^2 d\omega \quad (24)$$

The integral in (24) may be approximated by a sum of frequency numerical components (FNC) of $F_k(\omega)$ with as narrow as possible discrete frequency step $\Delta\omega_C$. Considering all the FNC of a band, from the lower (ω_{a_k}) to its upper one ($\omega_{b_{k-1}}$), the band k energy E_k may be conveyed into the approximation in (25). It is also possible to define the Accumulated Energy (26) at a specific FNC; n_c is the higher FNC.

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{x=a_k}^{b_{k-1}} |F(\omega_x)|^2 \Delta\omega_C \quad (25)$$

$$E_{ACC}(\omega_x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{j=x}^{n_c} |F(\omega_j)|^2 \Delta\omega_C \quad (26)$$

III. FILTERED FREQUENCY SPECTRUM METHOD (FFSM)

Fig.5 shows a functional block sequence of input-output data, each colored block representing a MATLAB or an ATP-EMTP simulation. The harmonic impedance of the electrode $Z(j\omega)$ consists of the FDSP ρ, ϵ , the magnetic permeability μ_0 that characterizes the soil, the electrode physical specification, and its relative soil position. The impedance is calculated using the TLM. The GPR $v(t)$, as a reference for comparison, is calculated as $v(t) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{Z(s) \cdot I(s)\}$ (see Fig.4); The Vector Fitting (VF) [12] technique is used to approximate the frequency-dependent harmonic impedance into rational function, characterized by residues and poles, to facilitate the computation of the GPR using recursive convolution method [13].

The FFSM comprises the following steps:

- 1) A lightning current $i(t)$ is chosen and the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is applied. The magnitude $I(\omega)$ is obtained for a large frequency spectrum (FS) and spectral energy density (25) is calculated; an algorithm based on the spectrum energy is used to optimize the frequency component selection ω_{ki} for each band, in accordance with (20);

Fig. 5: Steps to obtain the GPR: reference and FFSM methods divided into frequency domain (FD) and time domain (TD).

- 2) The FS of the input signal is split into three bands named low, mid, and high-frequency bands. Thus, it is adopted $n = 3$ in (20). Two cutoff frequencies are then necessary for a three-band splitting: ω_1 and ω_2 .
- 3) The grounding system circuit models ($EC1, EC2, EC3$) are built in ATP-EMTP software as illustrated in Fig.6. Each band provides a specific impedance Z_k (21) which is represented by a circuit model inserted in each GPR block;
- 4) The soil electrical resistivity and permittivity (ρ_k, ϵ_k) are assumed constant for each band but calculated at a representative frequency f_k , selected amid its frequency range. This selection is done by analyzing the distributed energy density of each band of the discretized frequency band.
- 5) The ρ_k and ϵ_k are used to build the specific circuit model for each band, which is incorporated in the ATP-EMTP software, as depicted in Fig.6.
- 6) The input signal, lightning current $i(t)$, is submitted to filters $F1, F2, F3$ and $F4$.
- 7) Finally, in the output, the resulting GPR is computed by a sum of the individual responses generated in the blocs $EC1, EC2$ and $EC3$.

The Transient Analysis of Control Systems (TACs) components of ATP were used to sum the output values, from the filters, and also build the TF filters. A user-defined MODEL was set up to represent the Heidler function to generate the input lightning current. The cutoff frequency f_2 (Hz), $(\omega_2/2\pi)$ is equal to 1 MHz. This is based to a certain extent on the analysis from [6] and the results from [3]. The cutoff frequency f_1 equals 100 kHz, approximately the Low-Frequency frontier per the International Telecommunication Union (ITU). The filters $F1, F2, F3$ and $F4$ used in ATP-EMTP (Fig.6) are of the first order. The number of FNC in band k , found through FFT, is $b_k - 1 - a_k$ (25); $Ene_k(a_k, b_k - 1)$ in (27a) is a vector for band k , its components are indexed by a_k up to $b_k - 1$, and each element is the calculated FNC energy; $D(\omega_x)$ in (27b) corresponds to the derivative of the distributed energy density of FNC. The FFSM uses the following three different methods ($M1, M2$ and $M3$) for a FNC selection inside the band k for ρ_k and ϵ_k calculation, summarized as follows:

- M1: **FFSM-Avg** selects, from FNC, the frequency component for ρ_k and ϵ_k calculation as the average frequency between upper and lower frequency in band k ;
- M2: **FFSM-Ene** selects, from FNC, the frequency component for ρ_k and ϵ_k calculation that corresponds to the found least absolute difference between the energy average of FNC in the band k range (27c) amid the elements of (27a);
- M3: **FFSM-EneW** selects, from FNC, the frequency component for ρ_k and ϵ_k calculation that corresponds to the found least absolute difference between the weighted energy average of FNC in band k range (27d) amid the elements of (27a);

$$Ene_k(a_k, b_k - 1) = [E_{a_k} \ E_{a_k+1} \ \dots \ E_{b_k-1}] \quad (27a)$$

$$D(\omega_x) = \frac{|F(\omega_x)|^2 - |F(\omega_{x-1})|^2}{\Delta\omega_C} \quad (27b)$$

$$EA_k = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\sum_{x=a_k}^{b_k-1} |F(\omega_x)|^2 \Delta\omega_C}{b_k - 1 - a_k} = \frac{E_k}{b_k - 1 - a_k} \quad (27c)$$

$$EW_k = \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{x=a_k}^{b_k-1} |D(\omega_x)| |F(\omega_x)|^2 \Delta\omega_C \right) / \left(\sum_{x=a_k}^{b_k-1} |D(\omega_x)| \right) \quad (27d)$$

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This paper employs the horizontal electrode in [14]: The horizontal electrode parameters are; radius $r = 7mm$; length $l = 12m$; depth $h = 0.5m$. The analysis are performed in three low-frequency soil resistivity values ($\rho_0 = 100, 1,000$ or $10,000\Omega.m$); $\epsilon'_\infty/\epsilon_0 = 12$; $\mu_r = 1$. The lightning current is represented as an impulsive current source injected at one tip of the electrode, as depicted in Fig.8.

The Heidler functions are used to represent the LS: **first return stroke (FRS)** (peak 30 kA, **front duration (FD)** about $7\mu s$): $m = 1, n = 2, I_{01} = 30$ kA, $\tau_{11} = 1.8\mu s, \tau_{21} = 95\mu s$; **subsequent return stroke (SRS)** (peak 12 kA, **FD** about $1\mu s$): $m = 2, n = 2, I_{01} = 16.73$ kA, $I_{02} = 7.42$ kA, $\tau_{11} = 0.25\mu s, \tau_{21} = 2.5\mu s, \tau_{12} = 0.2\mu s, \tau_{22} = 0.23ms$. The π -circuit parameters $R, L, C, 1/G$ of Fig.3 expressed in equations 11a to 11c were included in Tab.I. In this table, the circuit parameters of the Low-frequency band (LB), Mid-frequency band (MB), and high-frequency band (HB) correspond to Electrical Circuits (Fig.6) $EC1, EC2$, and $EC3$, respectively. The results were obtained using 20, 60, and 180 π -circuits for $EC1, EC2$, and $EC3$, respectively. In the filters pairs $F1/F2$ and $F3/F4$, the constant K is equal to $1.59e - 6$ for cutoff frequency $100KHz$, and $1.59e - 7$ for cutoff frequency $1MHz$, respectively;

It is worth noting the relation of these lightning parameters and the crucial data compiled in [11]: the cumulative percent of exceeding values distribution (50% percent of the cases exceeds the 30 kA, 12 kA, and 35 kA peak current for negative FRS, negative SRS and positive stroke, respectively; 50% of the cases exceeds the FD of $5.5\mu s, 1.1\mu s$ and $22\mu s$, respectively).

A. Filtering the Current Signal

The input signal's FS is divided into three bands: $k = 1, 2$, and 3 (see 20). Three different circuits ($EC1$ to $EC3$ in Fig.6) are created for each band following the filtered signal frequency range; the soil parameters are calculated based on a frequency elected from that range. Fig.7 shows the input signal (labeled as IC in the figure) and the three signals resulting from filtering, thus resulting in signals of high, middle, and low-frequency bands. This figure shows that the sum of these three signals precisely reconstructs the input signal. Thus, the proposed ATP-EMTP tool works properly (Fig.6).

Fig. 6: Circuit implemented in ATP-EMTP software for current filtering and computation of the GPR for each current.

Fig. 7: Original injected current IC and reconstructed current waveform (sum) of SRS.

Fig. 8: 12-m horizontal electrode used for the simulations.

B. Comparative Energy - First and subsequent return strokes

The lightning current of FRS and SRS are presented in Fig.9-(a), noticing their distinct characteristics: peak and front-times. By using (26), the data is normalized (based on the maximum value for each curve), resulting in $E_{ACC_{SRS}}(\omega_1)$ for SRS and $E_{ACC_{FRS}}(\omega_1)$ for FRS. The accumulated energy is seen in Fig.9a together with the relative accumulated energy, expressed by:

$$k_E = \frac{E_{ACC_{SRS}}(\omega)}{E_{ACC_{FRS}}(\omega)} \quad (28)$$

According to this figure, the relation k_E demonstrates that from low frequencies up to 10 kHz, both SRS and FRS have similar values $k_E \approx 1$. However, as the frequency increases, the relation k_E increases significantly between 10

kHz and 0.5 MHz. Finally, above 0.5 MHz, it converges to nearly 2, representing relatively high energy for SRS at higher frequencies. This characteristic influences the frequency selection in the band k either by using (27c) or (27d).

C. Time-Domain GPR waveforms

The GPR developed for the lightning currents of FRS and SRS considering the proposed circuit model in Fig. 6. These simulation results are organized as follows:

- In order to compare the maximum values generated in the GPR, assuming a conservative approach, the harmonic impedance of horizontal electrode is calculated assuming the frequency-constant soil resistivity of $\rho = 100, 1,000, \text{ and } 10,000 \Omega.m$, and $\epsilon_r = 10$. These parameters are kept constant the entire frequency spectrum of the lightning current. These results are labeled as **TLM-FC** (red lines).
- The reference response, used for final results comparison are plotted using the TLM and assuming the frequency-dependent (FD) soil electrical parameters from (14a) and (14b). The soils of low-frequency $\rho_0 = 100, 1,000 \text{ and } 10,000 \Omega.m$ are selected. These results are labeled as **TLM-FD** (green lines). The response from **TLM-FD** is obtained via convolution, given by

$$v(t) = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \{ Z(s) \times I(s) \} \quad (29)$$

- The simulation results are computed with the developed circuit in ATP-EMTP using TLM combined with the FFSM to select the adequate frequency for each band. It is assumed the FD soil electrical parameters from (14a) and (14b), with $\rho_0 = 100 \text{ and } 10,000 \Omega.m$. In this case, simulation results are labeled as: **FFSM-Avg** (solid blue lines), **FFSM-Ene** (dashed blue lines), and **FFSM-EneW** (black lines).

The GPR developed for the SRS are plotted in Fig.10 while those generated for FRS are plotted in Fig.11. According to these figures, as a general observation, the voltage (peak values of GPR) increases with an increase in soil resistivity, with the highest values generated by the TLM-FC condition. This

phenomenon occurs as the TLM-FC condition disregards the frequency-dependent nature of the soil's electrical parameters. As the frequency increases, the soil's conductivity also increases, making the soil more conductive at higher frequencies. The Fig. 10 demonstrates a reasonable agreement for soils with low resistivity, considering the responses obtained using the FFSM methods for the SRS, namely **FFSM-Avg**, **FFSM-Ene**, and **FFSM-EneW**. However, as soil resistivity increases, the differences between the methods become more noticeable. Notably, **FFSM-EneW** consistently provided the best performance across all values of soil resistivity compared to the **TLM-FD** condition. In contrast, the transient voltages obtained using the FFSM methods for the FRS, as shown in Fig. 11, exhibit excellent agreement with the responses for soil resistivity of $100 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$. However, as the soil resistivity increases, the differences become apparent. Among the methods, **FFSM-EneW** provides the most accurate results, yielding peak values that closely match those computed using the **TLM-FD** condition.

In order to quantify the difference in transient responses, the peak values of GPR are calculated for **TLM-FC**, **FFSM-Avg**, **FFSM-Ene** and **FFSM-EneW** and compared to those assessed with the condition **TLM-FD**. The Peak errors Pe_y is evaluated as:

$$Pe_y = \frac{|P_{TLM-FD} - P_y|}{P_{TLM-FD}} \times 100\% \quad (30)$$

Additionally, the signal energy error Ene_{e_y} is calculated as:

$$Ene_{e_y} = \frac{|Ene_{TLM-FD} - Ene_y|}{Ene_{TLM-FD}} \times 100\% \quad (31)$$

where y represents the corresponding values computed for **TLM-FC**, **FFSM-Avg**, **FFSM-Ene** and **FFSM-EneW**. The errors Pe_y and Ene_{e_y} are shown in Fig.(12(a1 and a2) and Fig.(12(b1 and b2) respectively. The three values for soil resistivity and the two current types (FRS and SRS) were considered. As shown in Fig.12, the Pe_y increases with increasing soil resistivity ρ_0 . The general results follow that the highest error in the peak values of GPR is obtained with **FFSM-Avg**, and the lowest is obtained for **FFSM-EneW**. All the figures' errors converge (lowest error) to FFSM-Wene method. Notice that TLM-FC (the highest error in each figure) is included to show the scenario for fixed soil parameters. These results can also be verified from the previous GPR waveforms; see the black lines (FFSM-EneW) compared to the green one (TLM-FD) in Fig.11 and Fig.10. Thus, the **FFSM-EneW** is the nearest to reference TLM-FD (obtained for reference using harmonic impedance), presenting the best performance of all FFSM methods. The errors are all lower than 5% except in one case due to the high soil resistivity.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a grounding system circuit model for a horizontal electrode buried in soil with frequency-dependent electrical parameters. The model simplifies the analysis by dividing the frequency spectrum of the injected lightning

Fig. 9: (a) Waveforms of the First return stroke (FRS) and Subsequent Return Stroke (SRS); (b) Norm.Accumulated Energy (NAE) and the Relative NAE.

current into various bands. Firstly, the electrical parameters of the horizontal electrode were calculated. The frequency spectrum of the injected lightning current is then divided into three distinct bands. For each band, a representative frequency f_k is selected based on a criterion that considers the distribution of energy density. This technique is denoted here as the Filtered Frequency Spectrum Method (FFSM), for which three distinct approaches, named here as **FFSM-Avg**, **FFSM-Ene** and **FFSM-EneW**, were tested. The method enables the Ground Potential Rise (GPR) to be calculated directly in the time domain using the ATP-EMTP software, utilizing realistic characteristics of the lightning current injected at the tip of the conductor and soil with frequency-dependent electrical parameters. The presented method, **FFSM-EneW**, is a time-domain process that is faster than **TLM-FD**, as the latter is obtained by inverse FFT from the product of the impedance and current. This traditional process is cumbersome due to the number of steps involved, as shown in Fig. 5. Results demonstrate that the proposed method **FFSM** associated with a simplified grounding system circuit model significantly agrees with the GPR developed for the first and subsequent return strokes. The approach **FFSM-EneW** exhibited the lowest errors at the peak values of GPR and the least signal energy errors. The best performance was also observed for soils with low and moderate resistivity. The highest peak values of GPR were obtained when the soil was modeled by its frequency-constant parameters (**TLM-FC**), reinforcing the importance of a more realistic approach for the soil, including its frequency-dependent electrical parameters. This method emphasizes the numerical energy derivative of the components, contributing to

TABLE I: R , L , C and $1/G$ circuit parameters for FRS and SRS

FIRST RETURN STROKE - FFSM-WEnE						SUBSEQUENT RETURN STROKE - FFSM-WEnE					
ρ_0 ($\Omega \cdot m$)	Band	R $\Omega \cdot m$	L mH	C	1/G $\Omega \cdot m$	$\rho_0 \Omega \cdot m$	Band	R $\Omega \cdot m$	L μH	C μF	1/G $\Omega \cdot m$
100	LB	6.70e-5	5.64e-4	2.60e-3	246.93	100	LB	6.70e-5	5.64e-4	2.60e-3	246.93
	MB	2.23e-5	1.88e-4	1.59e-3	693.90		MB	2.23e-5	1.88e-4	1.51e-4	690.4
	HB	7.44e-6	6.27e-5	2.09e-5	1750.49		HB	7.44e-6	6.27e-5	2.13e-5	1762.8
1,000	LB	6.70e-5	5.64e-4	1.42e-3	2369.7	1,000	LB	6.70e-5	5.64e-4	1.42e-3	2369.7
	MB	2.23e-5	1.88e-4	9.19e-5	5272.3		MB	2.23e-5	1.88e-4	8.76e-5	5167.2
	HB	7.44e-6	6.27e-5	1.34e-5	8925.0		HB	7.44e-6	6.27e-5	1.36e-5	9100.6
10,000	LB	6.70e-5	5.64e-4	7.81e-4	19477.4	10,000	LB	6.70e-5	5.64e-4	7.81e-4	19477.4
	MB	2.23e-5	1.88e-4	5.59e-5	23025.2		MB	2.23e-5	1.88e-4	5.36e-5	21976.1
	HB	7.44e-6	6.27e-5	9.39e-6	24576.5		HB	7.44e-6	6.27e-5	9.52e-6	25294.3

 Fig. 10: GPR waveforms developed for SRS. The plotted figures: TLM-FD, TLM-FC, FFSM-Avg, FFSM-Ene and FFSM-WEnE; The plotted figures for soils with: (a) $\rho_0 = 100 \Omega \cdot m$; (b) $\rho_0 = 1,000 \Omega \cdot m$; (c) $\rho_0 = 10,000 \Omega \cdot m$.

 Fig. 11: GPR waveforms developed for FRS. The plotted figures: TLM-FD, TLM-FC, FFSM-Avg, FFSM-Ene and FFSM-WEnE; The plotted figures for soils with: (a) $\rho_0 = 100 \Omega \cdot m$; (b) $\rho_0 = 1,000 \Omega \cdot m$; (c) $\rho_0 = 10,000 \Omega \cdot m$.

a representative frequency choice in each band for ρ_k and ϵ_k . Although a wide range of soil resistivity variations has been tested, different electrodes and lightning current waveforms must be analyzed in future works.

The Transmission Line Model (TLM) served as the basis for reference comparison and for the FFSM method. For future

work, the electrode impedance can be modeled using full-wave electromagnetic software, such as FEKO or CDEGS, where the GPR can be assessed by recursive convolution methods. The basis for the FFSM method always relies on filtering the frequency spectrum of the lightning current and the frequency-dependent soil parameters (FDSF) computed at the specific frequency of each band. Additionally, other physical factors,

Fig. 12: Relative Error for Peak and Energy

such as soil water content and porosity, can be included in the time-domain GPR analysis using the FFSM. It was shown that three voltages (outputs) at the simplified circuit model are generated individually, and the final voltage (GPR) is the result of the sum of each parcel. Under this strategy, the number of bands can be easily increased for greater accuracy in the results.

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